



Supplementary file 1: Fig.1

H-traps used to sample for *Stomoxys* flies across the three different ecological settings in northeastern KwaZulu-Natal



*S. niger niger*



*S. sitiens*



Supplementary file 2: Fig.2

Six *Stomoxys* species collected from the three ecological settings in north-eastern KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa



*S. boueti*

0.5 mm



*S. niger. bilineatus*

0.5 mm



*S. taeniatus*

0.5 mm



*S. calcitrans*

0.5 mm



500 μm



0.5 mm



0.5 mm



0.5 mm



0.5 mm



0.5 mm